

EFFECTIVE CRUSHING SIMULATION FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

Effective crushing simulation for complex composite structures requires not only consideration of material crushing behaviour at the “crush front”, but also prediction of structural response, including other possible damage and failure mechanisms, away from the crush front. This is achieved utilizing CZone technology embedded within a commercially available finite element program (Abaqus/Explicit).

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INTRODUCTION

Mounting pressures to lower emissions and improve fuel economy, while maintaining or enhancing vehicle performance, are focusing growing attention in the automotive and aerospace industries on increased usage of composite materials in order to reduce vehicle mass and help achieve these targets. The benefits of these materials are well-known, including a high stiffness-to-weight ratio, as well as a substantial capacity to absorb energy in an impact event.

Composite Crushing Behavior

Composite structures generally behave much differently than their metallic structure counterparts in an impact or crash event when subjected to large compressive and dynamic forces. To absorb the kinetic energy of the event, a metallic structure will typically undergo plastic deformations through various buckling and folding mechanisms that are induced. In contrast, a composite member subjected to substantial axial compressive forces will pulverize in a progressive manner from one end to the other as the “crush front” moves along its length. Efficient energy absorption can best be achieved when the moving crush front becomes essentially a continuous event, traversing steadily along the length of the composite member.

The crush front is characterised by numerous complex microscopic interactions between fibre and matrix. Attempting through simulation to capture these individually can be both costly and uncertain. And so simulation of composite crushing failure can prove difficult using conventional finite element methods.

Advanced Simulation Technology

CZone technology has been developed to bridge the gap between experimental observations regarding a composite material’s ability to absorb energy in an impact scenario and the need to also understand and reliably predict complex structural interaction and stability in a larger scale crash event. CZone technology has been incorporated as an add-on product for Abaqus/Explicit in order to provide a predictive capability for composite structure crush scenarios—the CZone functionality handles the material’s behaviour at the crush front, while the damage and failure models in Abaqus/Explicit deal with the integrity of the back-up structure.

Examples

This paper will demonstrate the CZone technology in action on some automotive and aerospace scale structures, and will identify the additional material characterization required to successfully predict their performance in crash.

A mass of 1150 kg. moving at an initial velocity of 9.1 m/s impacts a complex composite cone structure in an experimental sled test. Crushing of the cone progresses to a point where a large fracture develops suddenly in the transition region between the cone and its backup structure.

Simulation results predict well both the crushing response and the sudden fracture outside the crush front. Acceleration histories of the sled mass correlate well when comparing experimental data (blue) against simulation results (green).